

KASR TARTIBLI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR UCHUN TO'RTINCHI TARTIBLI RUNGE-KUTTA METODI

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Annotation: In this article, we use the fourth order Runge–Kutta method to solve fractional differential equations and their systems with the initial conditions. And we cover calculations of its values using the algorithms in the Python programming language. Solution is established to the different values of α which is the order of fractional differential equation.

Keywords: Caputo fractional differential derivative and integral, the fourth order Runge–Kutta method

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biz kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar va ularning sistemasi uchun boshlang'ich shartli masalalarni yechishni Runge-Kutta usulidan foydalanamiz. Hamda uning qiymatini hisoblash uchun Python dasturlash tilidagi algoritmdan foydalangan holda hisoblashni yoritib berganmiz. Yechim hosila tartibi α ning turli qiymatlari uchun chizilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Kaputo kasr tartibli hosila va integral, to'rtinchi tartibli Runge-Kutta metodi

Hozirgi vaqtda kasr tartibli integral va hosilalar nazariyasi funksiyalar nazariyasining tarmoqlaridan biri bo'lib, muhim amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo'lmoqda [1-6]. Kasr tartibli hosila va integrallarga asoslangan matematik modellashtirish, turli jarayonlar va hodisalar o'zgarishini baholashda, matematik biologiyada [7], gidrogeologiyada issiqlik va massa almashinish jarayonlarini bir xil bo'lmagan muhitda modellashtirishda [8-10], transonik oqimlarning elastoplastiklik muammolari, yarimo'tkazgichlar sohasidagi tadqiqotlar, epidemiologiyada, moliya va boshqa yo'nalishlarda e'tirof etiladi.

Kasr tartibli integrallar va hosilalar o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega va kasr integrallari va hosilalari bilan tenglamalarni yechishning analitik usullari har doim ham samarali emas. Shu bois ko'p hollarda biz sonli usullarga murojat qilmoqdamiz. So'nggi yillarda sonli usullar keng rivojlandi. Biroq, ushbu yo'nalishda erishilgan

muvaffaqiyatlarga qaramay, shunga o'xshash muammolarning umumiy sinfi uchun taqribiy usullardan foydalanishni nazariy asoslash masalasi ochiqligicha qolmoqda.

Aytaylik $\alpha > 0$ va $n = \alpha$ bo'lsin. Kaputo α kasr tartibli hosila quyidagicha ta'riflanadi:

$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_a^t (t-u)^{n-\alpha-1} \left(\frac{d}{du}\right)^n f(u) du$$

$a = 0$ uchun, quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = D^\alpha f(t).$$

Endi to'rtinchi tartibli Runge-Kutta metodida biz quyidagi kasr tartibli differensial tenglamani yechish uchun algoritm quramiz:

$$D^\alpha y(t) = f(t, y(t)), \quad y(t_0) = y_0, \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1,$$

bu yerda $y \in C^{p+1}([t_0, t_0 + T])$.

t_0 nuqta atrofida quyidagi tenglik o'rinli bo'lsin:

$$D^\alpha E(0) = D^{2\alpha} E(0) = 0, \quad E(h) = y(t+h) - y(t).$$

Quyidagi kengaytmadan taqribiy yechimga erishamiz:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + \frac{h^\alpha}{6\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (K_1 + 2K_2 + 2K_3 + K_4),$$

bu yerda $K_1, \dots, K_4$ isbotda quriladigan funksiyalar.

Isbot. Isbot oldingi holatdagi RK2 ga o'xshash.

bu yerda xatolik kengaytmasini kiritamiz:

$$E(h) = y_{n+1} - y_n = \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} D^\alpha y_n + \frac{h^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} D^{2\alpha} y_n + O(h^{3\alpha}) = \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} f(t_n, y_n) + \frac{h^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} D^{2\alpha} y_n + O(h^{3\alpha})$$

va uning α tartibli hosilasi:

$$D^\alpha E(h) = f(t_n, y_n) + \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} D^\alpha y_n + O(h^{2\alpha}),$$

va

$$y_{n+1} - y_n = C_1 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1 + C_2 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_2 + C_3 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_3 + C_4 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_4.$$

Shunga ko'ra:

$$E[h] = C_1 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1 + C_2 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_2 + C_3 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_3 + C_4 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_4,$$

bu yuerda:

$$K_1 = f(t_n, y_n),$$

$$K_2 = f\left(t_n + a_2 \frac{h^\alpha}{2\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, y_n + b_2 \frac{h^\alpha}{2\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_1\right),$$

$$K_3 = f\left(t_n + a_3 \frac{h^\alpha}{2\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, y_n + b_3 \frac{h^\alpha}{2\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_2\right),$$

$$K_4 = f\left(t_n + a_4 \frac{h^\alpha}{2\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, y_n + b_4 \frac{h^\alpha}{2\Gamma(\alpha+1)} K_3\right).$$

Vanihojat:

$$D^\alpha E[h] = C_1 K_1 + C_2 K_2 + C_3 K_3 + C_4 K_4 + C_1 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} D^\alpha K_1 + C_2 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} D^\alpha K_2 + C_3 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} D^\alpha K_3 + C_4 \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} D^\alpha K_4.$$

Endi $h \rightarrow 0$ quyidagiga kelamiz:

$$D^\alpha E[0] = C_1 K_1[0] + C_2 K_2[0] + C_3 K_3[0] + C_4 K_4[0],$$

$$f(t_n, y_n) = (C_1 + C_2 + C_3 + C_4) f(t_n, y_n).$$

Bundan esa, quyidagi tenglikka kelamiz:

$$1 = C_1 + C_2 + C_3 + C_4.$$

Biz olgan boshqa shartlardan (va $D^\alpha E(h) = 0$ dan):

$$\begin{cases} C_2 a_2 + C_3 a_3 + C_4 a_4 = \frac{1}{2} \\ C_2 b_2 + C_3 b_3 + C_4 b_4 = \frac{1}{2} \end{cases}$$

Vanihojat, quyidagi sistemaga kelamiz:

$$\begin{cases} C_1 + C_2 + C_3 + C_4 = 1 \\ C_2 a_2 + C_3 a_3 + C_4 a_4 = \frac{1}{2} \\ C_2 b_2 + C_3 b_3 + C_4 b_4 = \frac{1}{2} \end{cases}$$

Eslatma. Bu sistemaning yechimi yagona emas. Shuning uchun biz RK2 holatida bo'lgani kabi tanlaymiz:

$$C_1 = C_4 = \frac{1}{6}, C_2 = C_3 = \frac{1}{3},$$

$$a_1 = b_1 = a_4 = b_4 = 1, a_2 = b_2 = a_3 = b_3 = \frac{1}{2}.$$

1-misol. To'rtinchi tartibli Runge-Kutta algoritmidan foydalanib quyidagi kasr tartibli differensial tenglamani yeching.

$$D^\alpha y(t) = t^2 + \frac{y^2}{4}, y(0) = 1,$$

```
import numpy as np
import math
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.special import gamma, factorial
h=0.01
a=0.5
d=math.pow(h,a)/gamma(a+1)
t=[0]*11
y=[1]*11
def f(t, y):
    return t*t+y**2/4
print(str(t[0])+ ' ' +str(y[0]))
for i in range (len(t)-1):
    k1=f(t[i],y[i])
    k2=f(t[i]+d/2,y[i]+d/2*k1)
    k3=f(t[i]+d/2,y[i]+d/2*k2)
    k4=f(t[i]+d,y[i]+d*k3)
    y[i+1]=y[i]+d*(k1+2*k2+2*k3+k4)/6
    t[i+1]=i*d+d
    print(str(t[i+1])+ ' ' +str(y[i+1]))
plt.plot(t,y,'r^--')
plt.show(t,y)
0 `1
0.11283791670955128 1.0295142542920244
0.22567583341910255 1.0637396317812162
```

0.3385137501286538 1.1059938859407237
0.4513516668382051 1.1598555515289604
0.5641895835477564 1.2292341570655039
0.6770275002573076 1.3184755920620128
0.7898654169668589 1.4325209415435691
0.9027033336764102 1.5771463788799218
1.0155412503859615 1.7593277864019032
1.1283791670955128 1.9878026227926244

2-misol. Quyidagi kasr tartibli tenglamalar sistemasini yeching:

$$\begin{cases} D^{\frac{1}{2}}x(t) = t^2 + \frac{y^2}{4}, x(0) = 0 \\ D^{\frac{1}{2}}y(t) = t^2 + \frac{x^2}{4}, y(0) = 1 \end{cases}$$

```
import numpy as np
from mpl_toolkits import mplot3d
import math
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```



```
from scipy.special import gamma, factorial
#plt.style.use('seaborn-poster')
ax = plt.axes(projection='3d')
h=0.01
a=0.5
d=math.pow(h,a)/gamma(a+1)
t=[0]*11
y=[1]*len(t)
x=[0]*len(t)
def f(t,x,y):
    return t*t+y**2/4
def g(t,x,y):
    return t*t+x*x/4
print(str(t[0])+ ' ' +str(x[0])+ ' ' +str(y[0]))
for i in range (len(t)-1):
    k1=f(t[i],x[i],y[i])
    l1=g(t[i],x[i],y[i])
    k2=f(t[i]+d/2,x[i]+d/2*k1,y[i]+d/2*l1)
    l2=g(t[i]+d/2,x[i]+d/2*k1,y[i]+d/2*l1)
    k3=f(t[i]+d/2,x[i]+d/2*k2,y[i]+d/2*l2)
    l3=g(t[i]+d/2,x[i]+d/2*k2,y[i]+d/2*l2)
    k4=f(t[i]+d,x[i]+d*k3,y[i]+d*l3)
    l4=g(t[i]+d,x[i]+d*k3,y[i]+d*l3)
    x[i+1]=x[i]+d*(k1+2*k2+2*k3+k4)/6
    y[i+1]=y[i]+d*(l1+2*l2+2*l3+l4)/6
    t[i+1]=i*d+d
    print(str(t[i+1])+ ' ' +str(x[i+1])+ ' ' +str(y[i+1]))
ax.plot3D(t,x,y)
ax.set_xlabel('t')
ax.set_ylabel('x')
ax.set_zlabel('y')
0 `0 `1
0.11283791670955128 0.028695240749512047 1.0004865283749058
0.22567583341910255 0.06036013436943219 1.0038961626480236
0.3385137501286538 0.09811762210827879 1.0131728607627009
0.4513516668382051 0.14526605513424015 1.031308800883462
```

0.5641895835477564 0.2052994875727096 1.0613848076840098
0.6770275002573076 0.2819465506720434 1.1066316297842438
0.7898654169668589 0.37923638541051724 1.1705219631839099
0.9027033336764102 0.5016032699506425 1.2569064313706093
1.0155412503859615 0.6540471375542101 1.3702122451815708
1.1283791670955128 0.8423769549149305 1.5157327332247383

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Самко С.Г., Килбасс А.А, Маричев О.И. Интегралы и производные дробного порядка и некоторые их приложения. Минск, 1987.
2. Нахушев А.М. Элементы дробного исчисления и их применение. Нальчик, 2000.
3. А.К.Уринов, С.М.Ситник, Э.Л.Шишкина, Ш.Т.Каримов. Дробные интегралы и производные (обобщения и приложения): учебное пособие; учебно-методическое издание; на русском языке; А.Уринов и др. Фергана: изд. "Фаргона", 2022.-192 стр.
4. Уринов А.К., Каримов Ш.Т. Операторы Эрдейи-Кобера и их приложения к дифференциальным уравнениям в частных производных: монография; научное издание; на русском языке; /А.К.Уринов, Ш.Т. Каримов. Фергана: изд. "Фаргона", 2021. -202 стр.

5. Fractional Calculus and its Applications, lecture notes in mathematics/ Ed. Ross B. Berlin, 1975.
6. Constantin Milici, Gheorghe Drăgănescu, J. Tenreiro Machado, Introduction to fractional differential equations, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, 2019